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Social impact of nonprofit vocational training programs in Myanmar: Case study focus on Kayin and Mon State, Myanmar

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Abstract

The prime focus of the research case study is the social impact vocational training programs by the organizations empowering the youth for the community development in Myanmar. Providing statistic data analysis from combining of a questionnaire survey administered on the employees of the organizations and participants of the VTP (Voluntary Training Program) questionnaire, the author will conclude with its outcome, discussions and conclusion of this research thesis.

In the literature review, nature of non-profit organization (NGO) has difference policies and regulations in different regions and locations, so do the government and local authorities in Myanmar. Vocational training programs have different standards and methods to operate in community development and needs. Therefore, one of the ways is to indicate the social impact of the community and analyze the outcome of vocational training programs (VTPs) and non-profit organizations' (NGO's) action.

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This master's thesis came about (in part) during the period in which higher education was subjected to a lockdown and protective measures to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus. The process of formatting, data collection, the research method and/or other scientific work the thesis involved could therefore not always be carried out in the usual manner. The reader should bear this context in mind when reading this master's thesis, and also in the event that some conclusions are taken on board.

SALAI TUN LIN AUNG

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADB	Asia Development Bank
B4A	Bridge for All
CBO	Community Base Organization
CSO	Civil Society Organization
CSR	Co-operate Social Responsibility
EIP	English Immersion Program
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GNI	Gross National Income
ICNL	International Center for Not-for-Profit Law
IDP	Internally Displaced People
MBO	Mutual Benefit Organizations
MLCS	Myanmar Living Conditions Survey
MNEC	Mon National Education Committee
MOE	Ministry Of Education
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PBO	Public Benefit Organization
PCNC	Philippine Council for NGO Certification
SIE	Social Innovation Europe
SROI	Social Return on Investment
UNFPA	The United Nations Population Fund (The United Nations Fund for Population Activities)
VTP	Vocational Training Program
WH	Wide Horizons Program
WIN	Work Investment Network
VET	Vocational Education and Training program

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Myanmar is one of the largest countries in the South-East Asia with a total area of around 676,590 kilometers square. The total population is approximately 53.86 million with an annual population growth rate of 1.2 % (**ADB, 2019**). Due to the previous world's most isolated country by military regime, country poverty, social and economic was lowest in world.

In 2011 there was political changes happened in Myanmar that lead to the historic and fundamental transitions in every sector and more rapid changes had accelerated. Five years later in 2016, according to World Bank report still country poverty is below 32.1% of the national poverty line compared to countries in Southeast Asia. Average Gross National Income (GNI) per capita was US\$1,210 and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Growth Rate was 6.8% in 2017, forecast GDP for 2018/19 was 6.2 % (**World-Bank, 2019**).

Figure 1-1 Map of Myanmar, ethnic groups form Myanmar and ethnic minority states.

Nationwide implementation of development reformation, even though the current government wanted to implemented development projects, does not have the capacity to cover all the sectors. Thus, not only government took actions, but also nonprofit organizations were involved as in main roles. Nonprofit organizations had more involved important roles in Myanmar in recent years. Many nonprofit organizations have provided a myriad of vocational training programs in Myanmar, especially in ethnic minority states such as Mon and Kayin State of Myanmar. In 2018, majority of population 63.2% lives in rural area and only around 36.8% lives in urban area (**Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2018**).

Over half a million youths are unable to read and write, less than one in three aged 15-19 are go to school and around 9 million youths are out of school. University degree obtain population are only 7.3% of aged 25 and over (**UNFPA, 2017**). Furthermore, average high school student pass rates were 33% (226,085 students) in 6 years (2014-2019) (**MOE, 2019**). Moreover, total education budget for 2017-2018 academic year was only 8.53% of total nation budget (**(Union-Minister), 2017-2018, p. 13**). As a result, one in five youths ages 10 to 17 is working as a child labor in Myanmar instead of going to school (**Ehrke, 2017**). Lack of youth's education and skills make more vulnerable for country development.

1.2 Research Problem (purpose of this study)

In these regards, empowering youth by career literate is very important in country development period. Thus, various non-profit vocational school and training programs have been established throughout the country, most noticeably in Kayin and Mon State of Myanmar. In the Kayin and the Mon states, ethnic Kayin and Mon population are majority and several Internally Displaced People (IDP) camps have been largely established since became civil war-torn states.

Vocational Training Programs (VTP) are implementing important projects for empowering the youths in these regions, aiming to be benefiting socially and economically for target populations. However, assessment of the social impacts of the VTP are still lacking in Myanmar. (**Dees, J. G., Anderson, B. B., & Wei-skillern, J., 2004**). Therefore, this study will assess social impact of empowering youth by nonprofit organizations. Understanding of those social impact can be indicating future recommendation.

Globally economic and politics changes are highly effect to developing countries like Myanmar. The county with poverty, lack of finical support and social welfare has become bigger gap to compare with other regions (**Fung, K. K., & Craig, G., 2017**).

1.3 Research Objectives

To be able to identify the level of social impact of non-profit vocational training in Myanmar the impact analyses method has been used on non-profit organizations' survey and alumni survey. For this study, the main objective is to identify the level of social impact to community by VTPs. Therefore, three sub-objectives to focus study.

Objective 1: to understand the importance of VTP in Myanmar.

Objective 2: to assess the social impacts of VTP,

Objective 3: to compare the pros and cons of having VTP.

Effectiveness of vocational trainings is critical for non-profit organizations in Myanmar. Various Community Base Organization (CBO) are approaching several of programs to empower the youth. International donors and NGOs are willing to provide supports to improve youth community in Myanmar. Rapidly change of socially, economically and politically are highly effect to nationwide. Therefore, youth community need to efficiently and effectively train for future society (S. Mouzakitis, 2010). This research will provide social impact of non-profit vocational training in Myanmar.

1.4 Hypothesis

- Career of alumni are change after the VTP graduate.
- Community has been developed in certain way by support of alumni.
- Community and donors are more support in various way to nonprofit organizations by the impact of their projects.

1.5 General Research Questions

There will be two forms of research questions that focusing on to two main stakeholders that involved in this study.

To the VTP organizations,

- What are their aims and objective?
- Why did they choose these specific kinds of implementation?
- What are their future strategies?

To the alumni,

- What was the opportunities before and after VTP?
- How was the career and higher education development after the VTP?
- Which sectors or area of expertise are you working after VTP?

1.6 Conclusion

In this research study, the author will provide the scope, structure of the thesis organizations – discussion, significance, relevance, limitation and the data analysis, collection of the alumni-vocational program participants with the socio-economical factor of Myanmar.

In the next section which is the literature review, the author would like to express his concerns regarding the NGOs, CBOs and CSOs, global social innovative models which can be beneficial for the organizations, government of Myanmar and the voluntary community based programs linked with the social-economic growth of the country and study the global and national challenges associated with Myanmar.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

In the recent years, Myanmar is a country known for its religious and political crisis having first public elected government in 2016 having an impact on social, economic and environment aspects of the country. According to Myanmar Living Conditions Survey (MLCS) stated that in 2017 the percentage of the poor was 24.8% of the population. It also stated that in the same year the subsistence level was 1,590 kyat/adult/day. Lately, the situation has changed to an extent.

The author states that:

In late 1988 and 1989, almost twenty consultants from eight different organizations were involved in the project, the purpose of which was to identify NGOs that were able to contribute to Bank financed projects, and the ways in which any collaboration could take place. The willingness of governments to support the projects was an important aspect of the assessment. **(Bowden, P., 1990, p. 141)**

In this statement, how did the economic status of the Asian countries lead to the funds by the bank development programs and eight global organizations took part in the late 19th century. These non – profit organizations backed by the bank especially with the certain paths to mutually associate with the approval from the south east countries. The impact of the voluntary programs started during the 19th century with the projects funded by the banks. In Myanmar, at the same time, the political condition started to defoliate and there was a big impact in the social aspect. Well the other countries sort things out by development programs approved by governments but in Myanmar, the whole situation was at a threshold point.

In this chapter, we will discuss about the importance roles of NGOs, non-profit organizations, vocational programs and social innovative models. In this research study, the author would like to discuss about the importance of the voluntary/vocational programs by the organizations and the

social impact on the local communities in Myanmar, it was also considered suitable to give an overview of the social-economical factor of Myanmar.

2.2 NGOs

(Definition of NGOs, 2019) describe that “Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) is any non-profit organization that represent local, national or international level.” The NGO can be active in interest of any sector that support by communities. Sometime these organization can be established in the specific issues and special needs and support of community. Such as human right, environment or health. It means that, the organization base on people, community, society and working on indecently with self-governing in local to international level is an NGO. “The main feature of an NGO are: self-governing, private, not for profit and with an explicit social mission **(Vakil, 1997)**” **(Jordan, L., & Van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006, p. 8)**. The year book of International Organization define the NGOs as “organization which have not been founded and are not formally controlled by national government Union of international Association 2005” **(W.Witt, 2006)**. An NGO can be term in difference name as Civil Societies Organization (CSO), Community Base Organization (CBO), it deepens on the range of target areas and funding.

2.2.1 Types of NGOs

Basically, there are primarily two kinds of NGOs. They are ‘public benefit organizations’ (PBOs) and ‘mutual benefit organizations’ (MBOs). **(Jordan, L., & Van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006)**. Both types of organizations work in social, political and economic aspect on local to international level. Moreover, there can be categorize to two by activity of organization. First category is, operational NGOs that implement development project such as health, education, poverty and livelihood. Second category is advocacy NGOs which are organized to promote causes **(Folger, 2019)** in broader or specific area of such as rights, political decisions, environmental and justices.

2.3 International regulation of NGO

The World Bank and International Center for Not-for-Profit Law (ICNL) was developed a Global Standard Law for NGOs call “Draft Handbook”, unfortunately it has end in draft state with the various reason and disagreement. Thus, difference government, region and difference location have difference policies for NGOs. Sometime NGOs have their own rules and policies or difference regions. **(Jordan, L., & Van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006)..**

China has own regulations and policies for non-profit organizations, there are 3 categories or non-profit civil society organizations: Social organizations, foundations and private non-enterprise entities. **(Jordan, L., & Van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006).**

Indonesia policies of regulation toward NGOs are difference from china. Even Indonesia has long history and various NGOs across the country finally there are only two foundations (Yayasan) and association (Perkumpulan) **(Jordan, L., & Van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006, p.151)**. Majority of Yayasan organizations were established under the European legal system. On the other hand, Perkumpulan associations are legalize under the Minister of Justice and is an announcement in the appendix of the State Gazette.

Philippine have exceptionally and completely developed self-regulation for NGOs that certificate by Philippine Council for NGO Certification (PCNC).

Countries like Latin American countries, South East Asian countries have particularly policies and law for each sector. As for Myanmar, even there are fewer regulation has exist, regulation practice and enforcement are still weak in nationwide **(ICNL, 2019)**.

2.4 CBO/CSO

A Community Base Organization (CBO) and Civil Society Organization (CSO) are very similar to non-governmental organization (NGO). It is foundation on community and society, activities on non-profit and govern by independently. As an NGO, CBO and CSO function and serve specific operational or advocacy purposes with non-profit behavior. All most all the CBOs and CSOs are operate in locally and nationwide operation but not in the internationally.

2.5 Vocational/voluntary Program

Vocational program also known as a program of vocational education, that providing education training to a group of participants. The main purpose of the Vocational Training Program (VTP) is educating to participants who need to develop skills to engage in society efficient and effectively. In the VTP, educating to participants for career development, further study, sustainability, improve living hood and other skills. Now a day, VTPs let participants to learn effectively, creatively, individual and society development skills. Due to the effectiveness and sufficient VTPs are operating in every nation, most importantly, developing countries are highly rely on those programs (Europa, 2018).

2.6 Social impact of non-profit organization in Myanmar

Analyzing the social impact is identifying the outcome of present action which will be effect on the future of community outcome. Constantly should and need to monitor community environment activities. Civil society and non-profit organization play an important role in the community. Those organizations can have strong influence and lead community to different orientation direction. On the other hand, the direction could be interest of their own. Specific impact can be analyzed to specific individual organization project activity.

“Escobar's analysis forces us to rethink existing frameworks used to explore the relationship between religion and social change. The impact of Islamic fundamentalism was a recurrent theme in seminar discussions on NGOs in Bangladesh.” (Fernando, J. L., & Heston, A. W, 1997). In the later years, at the very end of the 19th century, the Islamic fundamentalism as stated in the above statement had a huge impact on Myanmar and cause significant amount of change in the part of religion and social change. The majority of the Myanmar population has been Buddhism and in the early 2000 slowly due to the inflation there was a rise of the Islamic population. And had a big impact on the country especially with the policies and regulations of the Myanmar government. Adversely had a social impact on the voluntary programs in Myanmar compared to the other South East Asian developing countries.

Author Amjad described that:

The broad objectives of the present study are to examine the impact of the global financial crisis as it folded during 2008 and 2009 on four major South Asian economies i.e., Pakistan, India, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka; identify policy actions taken to mitigate the adverse impacts of the crisis; and spell out a broader framework for macroeconomic and development policies to ensure sustainable and inclusive growth. (Amjad, R, 2010, p. 1).

Previously stated in the early 20th century, there four countries Pakistan, India, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka took a vital decisions on the social impact of the problems and created different frameworks to collaborate with the government with the development rules and regulations in order to make sure more sustainable and social development growth. During that time, Myanmar was going through a serious political crisis especially in 2006. Where the rest of the South East Asian countries had significant growth, Myanmar was dealing with its own political consequences; raging wars and there was a political unrest which hampered in the social aspects of the local communities like minority ethnic area that include Kayin and Mon States.

According to the statement of Kabeer (2005), there were certain small organizations that came up with voluntary programs and there was an impact in the south Asian countries. The evidence on

impacts reported by minimalist microfinance organizations as opposed to others which take a more "socially-oriented ... Findings from the Imp-Act program provide evidence on economic impact in the south Asian" (**Kabeer, N., 2005**). As stated, one of the programs called imp-act program was really beneficial for all the SE countries and there was a vital influence in the economical aspect of the voluntary programs which also had an impact socially. The results of the Imp-Act program had a good economical-social involvement in South East Asian countries.

While having the differences in between countries, the per capita of Myanmar is really low and its one of the poorest countries. People due to their low livelihoods and their social ways also made the non-profit organizations to help the societies encourage or promote the social development though social voluntary programs in the recent years which is associated with the political and markets to get involved. "Making a difference to livelihoods and capacities among poor people depends on NGO successes in fostering autonomous grassroots institutions and linking them with markets and political structures at higher levels." (**Edwards, M., 1999**). There was a good improvement in the social aspect when the NGOs played their vital roles in escalating the social aspects of the country specially some of the states in Myanmar. The interconnected 3 BL – Social, Economic and Environmental progress has been clearly shown when the micro finance organizations played their significant role in the local community.

Kim (2015) evaluated in the article that:

A comparative analysis of Korea, Thailand, and Indonesia reveals that each represents a differing mix of pressure and provision functions by NGOs in social protection. In Korea pressure seems to be the main role of NGOs; in Indonesia it is provision; while in Thailand pressure and provision are relatively evenly mixed. (**Kim, S., 2015, p. 2**)

While Korea shows stronger and more significance role in the social voluntary programs by the NPO while Indonesia and Thailand show a mix of everything. When it comes to stronger economical countries like Korea, and Thailand, Indonesia, they have shown some confusing pressure and provision functions by the non-profit organizations especially when it comes to social

protection. This reflects on the Myanmar social impact on the voluntary programs by an organization.

“There are few strong incentives for businesses in the region to adopt potentially costly initiatives when the marketplace is not demanding improved performance.” (De Simone & Bopoff, 1997). According to the author, the government funds and strong bank programs in certain South East Asian countries has helped to progress in the social performance. In Myanmar, there were changes after the political unrest in 2006. But initializing the expensive programs where the market is still at par and below compared to the rest of the south east countries which didn't help to improve the social-economic status and performance to the extend where Myanmar would have liked to be in the near future.

“Hence there is a need for developing systems at national level so that companies that have provided information on their environmental and social performance are rewarded with appropriate incentives, such as green procurement contracts.” (Anbumozhi, V., & Kanda, Y.,2005, p.16). As discussed earlier, the three bottom live social, economic and environmental, there has been changes in the developing and under development countries in South East Asia. The organizations had to lay out the performance report in regard to the environmental and socially. The performance is known as co-operate social responsibility (CSR). This will help any country to abide the foreign multinational organizations to help out the local communities – environmentally and socially. All these multinational organizations (NPOs) come up with a plan or organize and help the local communities. One of which is voluntary programs helping the students to learn, abide and dedicate to improve the local status of their own community, which helps the students to lay his hands to improve the performance of the local society and do his/her best to have an impact socially.

Frank, Longhofer and Schofer (2007) studied and discussed in the journal that “The role of domestic nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) in environmental policy reform in Asia.

Standard accounts treat NGOs as critical players in the policy process, responding to local environmental degradation and pressing states for environmental reforms.” (Frank, D. J., Longhofer, W., & Schofer, E. 2007). Few of the Non-profit organizations have also been involved in environmental sector for the local environmental degradation and making some changes to the reforms. It also impacts socially when it comes to voluntary programs by the non-profit organizations. It induces a lot of values and changes in the local community when it comes to all these programs.

Author Clark (1995) described that:

In some countries NGOs effectively play an oppositional role; while elsewhere NGOs seek to represent the voice of the weak and help them organize in their communities to achieve a more powerful voice in the making of decisions and the allocating of resources. (Clark, J.,1995, p. 593).

The Non-profit organizations do a play a vital role in regard to the poverty stricken people of a country and creates events and social welfare programs in their communities with the objective of changing the resources and decisions to make their land a better place to live in. Irrespective of which, the social impact of the voluntary programs in Myanmar are mainly forcing the social-economical driven society in midst of the political unrest. It can be seen the changes during the 20th centuries. From 2000-2010 and 2010-2020 there has been quite a lot of changes when it comes to the social-economic impact. The organizations as well as the students enrolled in the voluntary programs plays a vital role in uplifting the society.

“However, in terms of sustainability and empowerment of communities and other stakeholders, the partnership approach with targeted interventions.” (Wai K. T. et al. 2012). The author tries to make a statement in regard to the sustainability and empowerment of the community’s condescending about the non-profit organizations, stakeholders and the ways of the collaboration in between the organizations and the way to improve the voluntary programs designed in a

different way. Well, it has a greater input to the community building programs and encouraging the young students to be part of it once they finish their degrees.

Lorch (2008) indicated that:

There was little movement in the political situation between the end of 2005, when the government relocated to a new capital, Naypyidaw near Pinyinmana in the center of the country, and the end of 2007, when the military regime finally began work on a new constitution. **(Lorch, J.,2008, P.10).**

According to the statement, it clearly shows the political unrest and the changes that abruptly started to happen compared to the developments to the other South East Asian countries. In Myanmar, when the rest of the South East Asian countries started developing the funds and voluntary programs, Myanmar was still in the verge of start the revolution for the political crisis. The new constitution was part of it and helped to generate the socio economical aspects of the states like Naypyidaw. Naypyidaw is the center of the economical booming of the country and hence by 2007 the army, military regime started to consider some advancement in the new constitution of the country.

Johnson (2012) described that:

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reports that the USA has the highest inequality and poverty rate across OECD countries with the exception of Mexico and Turkey; likewise, social mobility is lower, redistribution of income by the government plays a smaller role, and the distribution of earnings is greater than other OECD countries (OECD, 2008). **(Johnson, M. P., 2012, p.4)**

According to the author states the report of the OCED which is known as Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development that even a first world country like United States of America has really poverty rate along with the other OCED countries like Mexico and Turkey. The scattering of the earnings is higher than the other countries compared to the social mobility

and income per capita within the OCED countries. This also reflects on the Asian/South East countries which have the similar values like the OCED countries. When it comes to Myanmar, one of the main first factor is economic. “Across Myanmar, impoverishment is increasing, with ever-larger proportions of the population unable to meet their basic needs” (Lorch, J. 2008). According to the author, it is evident by this statement that there is a lack of economic growth in the country which proves vital and have a good impact on the social development programs by the leading organizations in the country. It’s very difficult to differentiate, associated with the small-medium organization’s voluntary programs with the multi-national organizations. When it comes to the entrepreneurs and their enterprises in the country which again touches cooperate social responsibilities with the voluntary programs and has been underline in the following statement.

Recent research state that “Particularly because those of us who write about entrepreneurship are likely also to be engaged in the teaching of prospective entrepreneurs, we can expect to be led to focus upon details of their activities.” (Abreu, M., & Grinevich, V. 2013). It clearly shows that leading multinational organizations have more of an impact when it comes to the voluntary programs in regard to the small-medium organizations especially with the young workers going back to the community who have been involved in the voluntary programs. In respect with the young entrepreneurs who deals with the voluntary programs can also contribute to the community with their innovative ways and ideas to create an entire new world to their communities. The questions lie whether there are enough of entrepreneurs involved in the voluntary programs to resolve the problems of the society and put greater effort to their own community.

Furthermore, the author also states that the government plays a significant role in deciding the social impact of the voluntary programs and who to benefit in the future: the ongoing voluntary program students or the organizations? Peruzzotti and Smulovitz (2006) state that :

The politics of social accountability involve civic efforts whose goals are: first, to monitor the behavior of public officials and agencies to make sure they abide by the law; second, to expose cases of governmental wrongdoing; and third, to activate the operation of

horizontal agencies. Civic actors are making a crucial contribution to the enforcement of the rule of law. **(Peruzzotti, E., & Smulovitz, C. (Eds.). 2006, p. 48).**

The behavior of the government as mentioned in the three parts: the manner of the government officials influences the rules of the policies of these programs, the corruptions and bribing of the officials and finally the processes or procedure aligned with the profitability of the governmental officials. Corruption makes it difficult for the organizations to hold a strong ground to create the voluntary programs and further affects the students who were supposed to be designing the community thereafter.

There are few methods/frameworks that most likely impact the social development programs social return on investment (SROI), social accounting and audit, Triple Bottom Line, Balanced scorecard which affects the mix economy of welfare of Myanmar. As mentioned earlier, economic of the country largely play a significant role on the voluntary programs due to the association of the cooperate social organizations. Arvidson and Lyon (2014) restate form Nicholls in the Social impact measurement and non-profit organisations: compliance, resistance, and promotion journal that:

The Social Return on Investment (SROI) method, introduced through a government sponsored project, is one such evaluation framework, which explicitly aims to mirror the private sector model of assessing return on investment with the reporting of a ratio of investment to financial values of social benefit (Nicholls et al, 2008). **(Arvidson, M., & Lyon, F, 2014, p. 9)**

This statement shows the Social Return On Investment (SROI) the private organizations made pricing model showing the return on the financial investment values impacting the social benefits. This can be further assessed as the large of the funding has been approved by the government in order to attain the social benefits via the private sector. Arvidson and Lyon (2014) suggest that “Other approaches include Social Accounting and Audit (SAA), Balanced Scorecards, Triple Bottom Line accounting and Blended Value (Emerson, 2003)” **(Arvidson, M., & Lyon, F, 2014, p. 9)** also helped in assessing the whole ratio of the investment to financial values of social benefit

by the organizations. These reports are directly sent to the government in order to showcase the social impact to the higher authorities like United Nations.

Furthermore, there has been questions about the frameworks/approaches like Social Return on Investment (SROI), Social Accounting and Audit, Triple Bottom Line, Balanced Scorecard if these suit the needs of the government, organizations and the society. The author clearly mentioned and stated that:

While some question whether frameworks based on the private sector experience are entirely suitable, others argue that unless organizations use frameworks and language that are recognized by the wider system of decision-making in our mixed economy of welfare, the value and achievements of social purpose organizations will not be acknowledged. **(Gibbon & Dey, 2011, p. 68)**

The approaches have a good impact on the economy of the government and welfare of its people. Even has an impact on the private organizations to create voluntary programs as their part to play in the community. Apart from it, there are disputably methods in evaluating the reports concerning the objective over subjective indicators of the approaches. “There are also tensions around methods used in evaluations where for example some favor statistics and ‘objective indicators over ‘subjective’ case studies.” **(Hall, 2012)**. Citing as an example, author also indicates on the statistical behavioral aspects of the reports and other case studies. “The standardization of social impact reporting.” **(“Principles into Practice”, 2012)** Standardizing the social report will greatly play a good role when it comes to the frameworks/approaches for the governmental statistics, organizations CSR behavior and community will advance and progress with the voluntary programs and the local students getting involve with it. Hence, the organizations have to lead the show in order to direct the voluntary programs and submission of correct reports to the central government to data analysis. The small-medium and multinational organization have to take precaution and get involved with their organizational structures specially setting the standards and have a solutions when it comes to training and technical difficulties and assistance. In the following statement from Dees et al, (2004) stated that:

From Stoneman's perspective, the failures stemmed from a lack of training and technical assistance, coupled with the absence of a handbook from which organizations could learn. To reduce the risks of failure, a central organization would have to take responsibility for standard setting, quality control, training, technical assistance, and program development. **(Dees, J. G., et al., 2004, p. 32)**

The organizations have to take a lead and make sure to have the precautionary steps for the training, technical assistance, introducing project and program development within their internal organizational structure. Henceforth, it will help to companies to maintain and contribute to the society by involving the voluntary programs and the students can play a major role in their own community after finishing the programs. This thesis is about the social impact on introducing the voluntary programs by the organizations and how it affects the country overall and the involvement of the participants/volunteers getting back to improve their community and lead it from there.

In the article of Volkoff, Golding and Jenkin (1999) highlights that:

The definitional problem in their study of adult and community education in Victoria, Queensland and Western Australia. They operated from the premise that: "the ACE provider is both community owned and managed, and that it responds to the needs of a community related to its geographical location or to a more wide-ranging community defined through some common characteristic(s)." **(Volkoff, V., Golding, B., & Jenkin, J., 1999, p.24).**

It states the importance of the geographical location of a community in order for the organizations to improve and contribute to the community. This statement also introduces to the problems associated with the adult and community education in Australia. As a country, Myanmar is under develop and the needs of the community are more compared to the voluntary programs introduced by the organizations. In this literature review, the author particularly discuss about the organizations and voluntary programs in the later section of the literature review section and the findings of this thesis will help in future research of the social impact of the voluntary programs introduced by the organizations as their cooperate social responsibilities.

“Despite the methodological progress of related approaches this applies to the individual economic viewpoint and all the more to the macro-economic and State level. (**Griliches 1997, Welch 1986, Dürr 1996**)” (**Van Lith, U. 1998**). The author relates this reference article to the students of the voluntary programs and most of them are undergoing interns or trainees or continuing training in the organizations as apprenticeships or highly motivated school students and underlines the frameworks and approaches to have an idea of the economy of the country both in the federal and provisional state level.

Nevertheless, it also depends on Myanmar’s social environment which always become a big factor due to the political unrest situations at times. There are factors leading for hiring the students for the voluntary programs and the author relates to “Considerable progress has been made in regression and factor analyses and in distinguishing between parameters such as natural talent, origin and social environment, practical work experience, educational results, productivity, educational return and career opportunities.” (**Van Lith, U., 1998**) and this statement reflects on the qualities and attributes a participant carries such as good educational qualifications, work experiences, communication skills and outer activities, achievement, productivity and natural talent. And most importantly, career opportunities while completion of the voluntary programs and the career growth. Few of the participants either focusses on their own career and move forward to achieve greater acknowledgement and others goes back to the community to help their own community.

The end findings may not be satisfying taking various factors such as career opportunities, educational qualifications, impact of the social, economic and political condition of the different provincial states etc. “Results are frequently not convincing for various reasons. Above all the decision-making foundations are scarcely of any use for the individual and for companies and State authorities.” (**Van Lith, U. ,1998**). This statement shows that not only it has impact on the individuals but also reflects on the organizations and provisional authorities how well, they can

provide growth in their own community and boost their career after completion of the voluntary programs.

The Social Innovation Europe3 (SIE) notes that “social innovation can and must come from all sectors the public sector, the private market, the third sector, and individuals/household and that many innovations move between sectors as they evolve.” (SIE, 2012, p. 19).

Figure 2-1 Social Innovation Business (SIE) modelling

The model produced by (SIE, 2012) for the private and public sector market and mainly the third sector which supposedly to be individuals with the entrepreneurial ways of understanding the market and create and organize their own ways to transform the social innovation ethics. According to the SIE chart the formation of the flow chart leads to three different sections which includes state of the art leads to new field of research and the latter leads to the dimensions of social innovation. The state of the art again has three different parts which are creating shared value (Porter and Kramer, 2006; 2011), BOP Theory (Prahalad, 2004) and disruptive innovations (Cristensen and Raynor, 2003) (Michelini, L. 2012). The author suggests to the state of the art according to the whole scene of Myanmar which is a very unstable country in regards, to the economic and political situations; hence it will be easier for the organizations,

government and the society plays an active role in carrying forward the shared value which will benefit all the three main parts of the country when it comes to the social impact of the voluntary programs by the organizations in the county. BOP Theory which states the bottom of the pyramid wealth and income for the poorest of the social-economical group. It relies on the brand, venture capital and business and community partnerships within the country or with the relationships with the global organizations and the governments. According to the author, it deeply indicates on the business and community partnerships that proves to be a vital way of having a growth in the socio-economic sector of the country.

It also has an impact on the organizations creating the value to the community by voluntary programs with the innovative way of dealing with the country's crisis and benefiting the organizations and community. After the state of the art, the new field of research deeply implies to the social innovation of the low-income market. In accordance to the author, as a low per capital income country like Myanmar, one of the poorest countries in the world shows that social innovations like growing or the organizations that has been playing a major part in the role of the social voluntary programs needs to come up with the innovative thoughts and ideas to ensure the growth of the particular community and hence, developing an impact on the upcoming voluntary programs. This will also help the new small-medium size organization put their social innovation to help the community to grow in an efficient way. Furthermore, coming to the last part of the chart, the dimensions of the social innovation consists of three different section: business models, product & process and communication. "Innovative business models can generate different types of enterprises as new age enterprises, social enterprises, community-based enterprises, hybrid organizations and inclusive businesses."(Westall 2007; CII-ITC CESD 2010) According to the author, innovative business and community partnership models such as social, community based and hybrid firms which is regarded as the new age enterprises will definitely play an important role in Myanmar creating a whole new era of the socio-economic growth of the country. Going further, innovation helps in creating a product and helps in a total new process that can be layout in the social platform.

According to the author, "Innovation can refer to the way in which an idea, a product or a service can be spread. It is the process by which an innovation is adopted and gains acceptance by members

of a particular community.” (Surry 1997). This innovative ways of creating a product and processing it can be developed and have an important social impact on the Myanmar’s community and help in growing it. One of the ways is by the organization’s voluntary programs in Myanmar’s provisional states. The last step of the dimensions of the social innovation is communication. Communication is greatly important in order to make sure the service of the product can be developed and process smoothly. The author focuses on the communication in between Myanmar’s government, the private-public organizations and the community partnerships. The Figure 2.1 SIE chart definitely shows the significant ways of approaching the model towards Myanmar and its provisional states.

The SIE chart, dimensions of the social innovation sometimes with the increase of the products there are increase in the services. The author states that “With the number and range of services increasing. But there have also been failures, with some initiatives failing to survive commercially once funding has ceased.” (Kurpius, D. D., Metzgar, E. T., & Rowley, K. M. (2010). According to the article, the author likes to mention with the increase in the demand and supply of a product there can be failures with the initiative programs and the funds from the government or from the private organizations can be stopped for any reason. So, it cannot be always a win-win situation when it comes to social innovative products and its services. As a country, Myanmar has to have a careful watch on their social innovative products and its services.

The author states “The idea that it is good for organizations and people to be more accountable is widespread in many societies, even if the word does not translate well into all languages.” (Lister, 2007). In certain terms, the author wants to relate to the propositions or projects can be the best implications to most of the enterprises/firms and the local community. It also shows that the proposition or the projects will not be good for some societies and the provisional states of Myanmar should correspond the propositions/ideas to the local community as the best way they can. With the uncertainty of the governmental political issues also plays a negative role cause, they won’t be able to give proper attention to the local community and the expression the propositions/projects to the community. So, either ways, the communication of the organizations,

government and the community partnership enterprises will be at a fair ground to progress for a better service to the community via voluntary programs.

In a country like Myanmar, due to the lack of the communications within the organizations, government and its people there might be questions on the behavioral factor of an organizations, its communication with the government and the local community, the mission, visions and the values of the organizations with the policies and regulations. In one of the articles (**Bakker,2002**) states “There is a wide variety of definitions of accountability used or assumed by people working on questions of organizational transparency, responsiveness, ethics, legitimacy and regulation, whether in relation to governments, corporations, NGOs or other organizations”. The author relates to the fact that Myanmar is an unstable country that can create loop holes and there can be a lot of questions and responsibilities for the government, big cooperation’s and other enterprises by the Burmese citizens.

The organizations are the main part for the social impact of Myanmar and its provisional states. It can be seen in spite of the political unrest there has been significant amount of community based organizations and non-profit organizations helping out with the voluntary programs in order to reach the community related partnerships in order to help the society with their needs. The youth as the voluntary based programs plays an important role in the future of the community despite losing out opportunities for their own career growth and leading a more professional life. The organizations and the vocational programs – participants play a major role despite of the unstable socio-economic status of Myanmar.

2.7 Organizations- CBO, CSOs and NGOs:

“The last decades have witnessed an extraordinary growth in non-governmental organizations (NGO) in all spheres of human activities worldwide, especially in developing countries.” **(Bromideh, A. A. (2011))** the author relates to the global increase of the non-profit/governmental organizations which includes the developing and under developing countries such as Myanmar, Nepal, Mexico, Turkey. With the increase of the number of the organizations, Myanmar has seen growth in this aspect of the society leading to promising socio-economical community growth with the number of increase voluntary programs by the organizations.

In the statement “The experiences of 18 development agencies with seed projects in Africa, Asia and Latin America are documented...to assess the comparative advantages of the different types of organization.” **(Cromwell, E., Wiggins, S., & Wentzel, S., 1993)** shows a lot of the countries from the continents like Africa, Asia and Latin America have number of developing firms/enterprises securing the data collection for the records and reporting the correlative merits of the organizations with the voluntary programs. With the community based organizations the progress and the evaluation of their projects/programs leads to the decision making of the public on the creation of the advanced programs and relates to the statement “The evaluation of a program after its completion to judge whether the public participation program furthered progress”.**(Rafique, Z., & Khoo, S. L.2018)**. The acknowledgment by the Burmese citizens in their own community shell will definitely leads to the concerns and priorities that should be given by the organizations in order to have fruitful programs.

Certain voluntary programs community driven development programs in the under-develop and developing nations have been associated with the country’s institutions and enterprises for the growth of the urban development and planning. In the statement “Community-driven development (CDD) programs, facilitated by decentralization, in developing countries have made community-based organizations (CBOs) key partners in new, participatory institutional arrangements for urban development and planning.” by **(Das, A. 2015)**. The author shows the interests of the Burmese

citizens even the urban development is fairly low than the other nations due to the social-economical backward society. Once the urban development and planning done properly by the government the funds can produced from the organizations and can be input the growth of the urban cities. Likewise, once the urban cities develop the rural towns or villages can also be part of the development and planning even through the voluntary programs led by the organizations. They can be associated to the international funding and make a prosperous growth.

Number of international non-profit organizations from the first world countries like United Kingdom and Canada can been seen helping out the under develop countries through funds and aid to the poor countries like Latin, African and Asian countries. In the statement below, the author “A number of Canadian NGOs, for instance, work with the Canadian International Development Agency in providing aid to developing countries” (**Williams, A. (1990)**), Canadian International Development Agency has provided funds from the early days of the 20th century “Since 2000, Canada has provided over \$180 million in official development assistance to Myanmar, primarily through international humanitarian assistance and support of multilateral institutions. Since 2013, after Canada lifted most of its sanctions, over \$95 million have been disbursed to Myanmar through all channels.” (**Canada, 2017**).

As of the leading countries, it has executed voluntary programs associated with the international advancement needs and directive measures from the Myanmar government through the voluntary programs associated with the international organizations and civil society in order to reduce the rural poverty areas of the country.

There is a huge impact on the international funding and aid due to the government/market failure. In the statement “Public sector provision of improved seeds in developing countries has often fallen foul of government failure, while commercial seed supply has faced unusually high transactions costs and some market failure.” (**Wiggins, S., & Cromwell, E., 1995**). Certain problems an organization can face is the span of the organization in Myanmar which lead to a lot

of organization closure due to the influence of the government, funding ceased or economic impact. Other Asian countries such as Japan, also statement the need of the voluntary programs by the organizations that reflects in the progressive development approach especially by the community based organizations associated with non-profit organizations stated by **(Hirata, K, 2002)**.

“The growing role of NGOs in ASEAN ... economic commissions, as well as many of the specialized agencies, all sponsor regional meetings at which NGOs either participate ... For example, in September 1997 in Kuala Lumpur the NGO Forum on Social Development in Asia.” **(Aviel, J. F, 1999)**. Intergovernmental organizations like Association of Southeast Asian Nations helps in creating meetings to collect data and help to see the overall development in the South East Asian countries. The author states the involvement of the social development by the provisional states of Myanmar with their regional meetings such as foundations like Myanmar Development Network helps in analyzing the CBOs, NGOs ad CSOs in Myanmar with their data collections and market analysis provides unique information which can be further discussed by the organizations which intends to create the voluntary programs.

“A conspicuous trend in the development of the contemporary world is the growing role of nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) in politics, the economy, and sociocultural progress.” **(Diachenko, S. ,2007)**. The author relates this with the advancement of the part of these CBOs, NGOS, and CSOs and directly has impact on the governmental politics, country’s economy and social development growth. In Myanmar, the various sections are very tangible and can have an impact due to political unrest, unstable economy and social-religious disruptions and chaos.

2.8 Vocational Programs – Participants

When it comes to the voluntary programs the author states (**Chamberlain, C. J., 2003**) “Able to engage citizens in their community in a variety of programs including the ... bring citizens together in a coordinated effort that through networking can lead to enhanced ... recreation leader attributes and community social capital as surveyed through volunteer samples” The networking through the various platforms plays a vital role in bringing the citizens of Myanmar and with some coordination it can lead to progressive ways to boom the social-economic growth. The vocational programs indeed help the participants/volunteers to together and discuss about their different methods/approaches to toward uplifting their communities.

On the other hand, one can show the number of increasing volunteers/participants such as cooperate social responsible cooperate as well as social entrepreneurs getting involved with the volunteer programs. In the statement by (**Creyton, M., 2004**) “Engaged in community building and capacity building projects, and to the emerging group of volunteers such as corporate volunteers, social entrepreneurial volunteers.”; can be related to the Myanmar situation of lack of volunteers/participants who return back to the community after completion of the voluntary programs in the organizations. The Burmese citizens, the other name for the citizens of Myanmar should understand the value of getting engaged with the community and develop community based projects for the social-economic growth of their provisional states as well as Myanmar as a country.

“Placed on experienced volunteers, their intentions to continue to engage in voluntary action may ...entering the past experience factor estimated total number of months volunteered in one's been mandated to volunteer with those who had been assigned to choose to volunteer.” (**Stukas, A. A., Snyder, M., & Clary, E. G. , 1999**). In this statement the author suggests of bringing in experience international or local volunteers to encourage the community based projects and show the light at the end of the voluntary programs held by the organizations. It is very important for

the experience volunteers/participants in Myanmar plays a vital role in between the time of completion of the voluntary programs and after their graduation their priority to get engaged in order to help in growing their social-economical factor in their community. The international volunteers should support the weak social cultural societies in Myanmar and help to improve the country's growth by creating a good communication with the organizations and local societies.

The question here lies is "How many voluntary organizations are you involved with?" and ... less predictive power than number of organizations, the number of hours volunteered per week." **(Oman, D., Thoresen, C. E., & McMahon, K., 1999)** which clearly shows the involvement of the organizations and their criteria of number of hours volunteers spend with the various organizations in order to develop experience and knowledge of their local society drawbacks and would help in bringing it the (SIE) innovation social ideas to bring out products and how to service and process the products.

In this statement, "Programs geared toward encouraging teenagers to volunteer in the expectation this might keep them out of trouble will not work if this encouragement seems to limit the voluntary nature." **(Wilson, J., & Musick, M., 1999)** the author emphasis on the youth's involvement which will help them to pass through the insignificant problems that they can create while being on substance abuse, harming the fellow youths/co-worker. The source of inspiration to join the voluntary programs in the institutions is very important to hold the grounds for the future of the voluntary programs for the community growth.

"Coordinated vocational program that emphasized competitive employment interventions for the residential." **(Bullis, M., & Cheney, D., 1999)**. The voluntary programs by the organizations in Myanmar should focus and target on employing the youths who are involved with these programs. Since the job market is competitive and the youth tends to work on their own career growth losing the significant meaning of the voluntary programs and the involvement with the community based social project after graduation/completion of the programs.

“Publicly subsidized for-profit and non-profit job-training service providers, namely whether organizational form influences client enrolment, service delivery activities, or performance, as measured in terms of participant outcomes.” (Heinrich, C. J., 2000). This statement reflects on the on board job training for both profit and non-profit organizations in Myanmar should create influences participants enrollment for the citizens of Myanmar, service delivery activities such as volunteering/entrepreneurial projects or community building programs which will have in the performance of the youth/participants in regards to their career growth and results.

“Non-profit-distributing, i.e., not returning profits generated to their owners or directors ... Organizations, Feasibility Study on Obtaining Information on the Economic Activities of Non-Charitable Nonprofit.” (Salamon, L. M., & Anheier, H. K., 1996). Sometimes, in the name of the CBOs, NGOs and CSOs the directors/owners tend to spend the funds and aid toward unnecessary needs of the enterprises or for their own profits and shows the funds has been used as miscellaneous costs of the company. To obtain the correct data of the CBOs, NGOs and CSOs, the state/governing bodies have to be vigilant in Myanmar so that the aid/funds goes in the right source and benefit the community. It also encourages the participants to believe in the system and move forward with their societies.

“Non-profit, welfare reform, contracting out ... The participation of non-profit agencies in welfare reform dates back to the early WIN programs and has expanded ... and training services funded by the Work Investment Act.” (Hasenfeld, Y., & Powell, L. E., 2004). The involvement of the organizations welfare reform programs such as Work Initiative Network (WIN) is an employment program to help and encourage the adults with psychological problems to land up with a job. Myanmar has number of youths specially with substance abused history and associations like WIN and Work Investment Act do fund the voluntary programs of the organizations via consultations and career counselling and training to those. In theory, they are more approachable to work for their community even though initially they might prove to reluctant to work depending on individual situation.

In this statement, after finishing the vocational programs, the youth with the educational qualifications earn their diploma and degree that is valued in the market. Author state that:

On completion of formal VET, successful learners receive a degree or diploma which is valued in the labor market. The value of this certification has been explained in terms of signaling to employers the potential skills and abilities acquired through the VET experience. **(Dalziel, P., 2017, p. 143)**

The Burmese youth and participants of such voluntary programs has lavage over the other youth cause of their knowledge and experience while they gain during their educational life. In regard to that, they are entitled to find their way higher up in the building the community projects or creating more programs with the help of their family members and thorough networking with their own communities. Even the professors can guide and advise the participants with these projects/programs. “Own employment through family contacts, neighborhood networks, or short-term volunteer job...for ongoing services, providing support for staff training, program development...Efforts to improve employment opportunities will involve cooperative with other agencies.” **(Will, M., 1983)**. In Myanmar, there are training services to get involved with the community and projects/programs development and enhance the job employment rate in respect to the other consultants/agencies. The youth can gain a lot by opting the right community-based projects or programs and enhance their career along with development of their own community.

2.9 Conclusion

The conclusion of the literature review shows the global challenges of the citizens, governments and organizations which includes directive measures and propagandas of the Asian/South East Asian specially leading to the findings and results of the social impact of the voluntary programs in Myanmar. The literature review also concludes with some important facts and figures underlying the problems and challenges that Myanmar can face when it relates to the organizations and voluntary programs which is precisely the main part of findings and results in this thesis.

It also shows the SIE chart which encourages the organizations to develop social innovation products and services via voluntary programs and how it impacts the youth who receives this voluntary program. Due to the environment of the country's political and economic unitability, the youth either choses to continue with the career growth or return to the local community to grow with the help of the programs which indicates in the next section of the thesis.

2.10 The various elements found in different scholarly articles are summarized.

Author, Year	The social impact of the VTPs in this research study.	Elements of the social Impact from a broader perspectives, best practices and terms.
1. Bowden, P., 1990	The government funded project for the VTPs, international project to improve community needs.	Government funded project, Bank finance project, international organization to improve under develop country's community needs.
2. L. Jordan, L., & van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006, p. 8.	Non-pro org for the social mission governing and private organization.	In the border perspective of nonprofit organization for social mission, governing and provide organization - Public benefit organization and mutual benefit organization.
3. Folger, 2019	Operational NGOs to development projects (VTPs).	Operational NGOs with development projects and advocacy NGOs to promote particular causes.
4. Fernando, J. L., & Heston, A. W., 1997.	Buddhism, Christen and Muslim existing framework between religion and social change in Myanmar.	Religious fundamentalism/ existing framework between religion and social change.
5. Amjad, R. 2010.	Framework of the VTPs for sustainable and social development growth.	South East Asia economy finical crisis-framework for micro economic and development policies to ensure sustainable growth.

6. Kabeer, N. 2005	Volunteering program by the small organization having the impact in the SEA countries organize by the small organization.	Volunteering program by the small organization having the impact in the South East Asia countries, finding form the IMP / Act program for the development of economic aspect in the SEA countries.
7. Edwards, M. 1999.	Good economical social involvement in Myanmar through Via micro finance organization, improvement of the local community needs.	Improvement of the community needs associate with the NGOs success in fostering grass roots institution /market and political structure.
8. Kim, S.,2015.	NGOs social protection, NPOs social volunteering program in Myanmar.	Social protection- role of NGOs in Indonesia and Thailand, mix of pressure and provision function by NGOs.
9. Anbumozhi, V., & Kanda, Y. 2005.	Social economic and Environmental development, corporate social responsibility - developing systems.	Environmental and social performance- incentives-green procurement, developing system in national level.
10. Frank, D. J., Longhofer, W., & Schofer, E. 2007.	NGOs social, economic and environmental aspect of VTPs.	Roles of NGOs - environmental policies reform- policies process local environmental degradation.
11. Clark, J. 1995.	NGOs-Community development – decision making and allocation of resources.	NGOs-Community development – decision making and allocation of resources.
12. Wai, K. T., Htun, P. T., Oo, T., Myint, H., Lin, Z., Kroeger,	Empowerment of communities, sustainability partnership approach with target intervention (VTPs)	Empowerments of communities, sustainability, state holders, partnership approach with target intervention

A., ... & Petzold, M. 2012.		
13. Lorch, J. 2008.	Military region- new constitution and political crises in Myanmar.	Military region- new constitution and political situation.
14. Abreu, M., & Grinevich, V., 2013).	Teaching of perspective entrepreneurial through VTPs for potential skills.	Teaching of perspective entrepreneurial to focus on the activities.
15. Peruzzotti, E., & Smulovitz, C. (Eds.), 2006.	Corruption, behaviors of government officer's wrongdoing.	Politic of social accountability involve in civic effect – public official to abate the law and expose the government wrongdoing, activate the operation of horizontal agencies.
16. Dees, J. G., Anderson, B. B., & Wei-Skillern, J., 2004.	Lack of training, technical assistance, program development -organization -VTPs.	Lack of training, technical assistance, program development, quality control. Standard setting.
17. Volkoff, V., Golding, B., & Jenkin, J., 1999.	Adult and community education, geography location, wide ranging community in Myanmar VTPs.	Adult and community education, geography location, wide ranging community in Australia.
18. Van Lith, U., 1998.	Parmenter of VTPs natural talent, origin and social environment, practical work experience, educational results, productivity, educational return and career opportunities	Natural talent, origin and social environment, practical work experience, educational results, productivity, educational return and career opportunities
19. Kurpius, D. D., Metzgar, E. T., & Rowley, K. M., 2010.	VTPs – initiatives – frailer – increase services	Increase in the range of services- failed - initiatives - failing to survive -will funding has ceased.

20. Surry, D. W., & Farquhar, J. D., 1997.	Social Invocation business model, Social impact of VTPs in Myanmar communities	Social Invocation business model – ide, product or service member of the particular community
21. Lister, R., 2007.	Organizations, VTPs, participant, accountable language barrier in Myanmar	Innovated idea for organization and people in many societies is widespread, language barrier
22. Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B., 2002.	VTPs- organization - organizational transparency, responsiveness, ethics, legitimacy and regulation, whether in relation to governments, corporations, NGOs.	Organizational transparency, responsiveness, ethics, legitimacy and regulation, whether in relation to governments, corporations, NGOs.
23. Griliches, Z., 1997.	Microeconomic and state level in Myanmar individual economic viewpoints – methodological progress of social innovated models approaches.	Microeconomic and state level individual economic viewpoints – methodological progress.
24. Michelini, L., 2012.	VTPs - Social innovation – public sector – private market the third sector and individual in Myanmar.	Social innovation – public sector – private market the third sector and individual.
25. Bromideh, A. A. 2011.	The growth in NGOs in all spheres of socio-economic activities worldwide - developing countries.	The growth in NGOs in all spheres of human activities worldwide specially in developing countries.
26. Cromwell, E., Wiggins, S., & Wentzel, S. 1993.	Seed community projects in Myanmar assess the comparative advantages of development NGOs and CBOs.	Seed project in the Africa, Asia, Latin America, assess the comparative advantages of development agencies / organizations.
27. Rafique, Z., & Khoo, S. L., 2018.	Public participant vocational program, evaluation of the VTPs.	Public participant program, evaluation of the program.

28. Das, A., 2015.	CBOs and NGOs – urban/ rural areas development training and planning.	Community-driven development (CDD) programs, CBOs – key partners – urban development training.
29. Wiggins, S., & Cromwell, E., 1995.	Public sector of improve seeds in Myanmar, government and market failure.	Public sector of improve seeds in developing countries, government failure, high transaction cost and market failure.
30. Williams, A., 1990.	International NGOs, CBOs providing aids to Myanmar.	Canadian, international development agencies NGO providing aids to developing countries.
31. Hirata, K., 2002.	Myanmar the needs of VTPs, progressive development approach by CBOs and NGOs.	Ancient countries – Japan the needs of VTPs, progressive development approach by CBOs and NGOs.
32. Aviel, J. F., 1999.	The growing roles of NGOs to participant in the regional meeting associate with the economy commission and specialize agencies.	Economy commission – NGOs / specialize agencies – regional meetings. Kuala Lumpur NGO forum on social development in Asia.
33. Diachenko, S., 2007.	VTPs and growing NGOs in Myanmar - politic, economic and social cultural progress.	The role of NGOs in politic, economic and social cultural progress.
34. Dalziel, P., 2017.	Completion of VTPs, successful learner, the value of certification potential skills and abilities.	Completion of VET, successful learner, the value of certification potential skills and abilities.
35. Chamberlain, C. J. 2003.	Community programs - bring community together - networking – VTPs in Myanmar.	Community programs - bring community together - networking – community social capital – volunteer samples.
36. Creyton, M. 2004.	Engagement in the community building, capacity projects – emerging group of volunteers – corporate volunteers - social entrepreneurial in Myanmar.	Engagement in the community building, capacity projects – emerging group of volunteers – corporate volunteers - social entrepreneurial.
37. Stukas, A. A., Snyder, M.,	Duration of the volunteering programs placement of experienced volunteers in VTPs in Myanmar.	Duration of the volunteering programs placement of experienced volunteers.

& Clary, E. G. 1999.		
38. Oman, D., Thoresen, C. E., & McMahon, K. 1999.	Involvement of volunteering organization duration of the program – number of hours at VTPs.	Involvement of volunteering programs, less predictive power than number of organizations.
39. Wilson, J., & Musick, M. 1999.	VTPs programs to encourage the youth.	VTPs programs – encouragement of youth to volunteer – limit the voluntary nature.
40. Bullis, M., & Cheney, D. 1999.	Coordinated vocational program - contribution to the local community.	Coordinated vocational program - competitive employment interventions – contribution to the local community.
41. Heinrich, C. J. 2000.	Profit and non-profit job training service provider – client enrolment - service delivery activities – performance - participant outcomes.	Publicly subsidized for profit and non- profit job training service provider – client enrolment - service delivery activities – performance - participant outcomes.
42. Salamon, L. M., & Anheier, H. K. 1996.	Economic Activities of Non-Charitable Nonprofit - nonprofit disturbed for the organization.	Economic Activities of Non-Charitable Nonprofit – nonprofit feasibility study on obtaining information – nonprofit disturbed.
43. Hasenfeld, Y., & Powell, L. E. 2004.	Nonprofit welfare reform contracting and training services.	Nonprofit welfare reform contracting and training services.
44. Will, M. 1983.	Own employment - family contacts - neighborhood networks, short-term volunteer jobs - ongoing services - support for staff training - program development - improve employment opportunities with VTPs in Myanmar.	Own employment - family contacts - neighborhood networks, short-term volunteer jobs - ongoing services - support for staff training - program development - improve employment opportunities.

Table 2-1 Scholarly articles summarized

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Study Area

In any organization manager can be increase or decrease the level of collaboration with organizations by networking. As for a non-profit organization, working together with other organization not only important and valuable for self but also for the community too. The impact of collaboration with other is always higher than expected.

Difference country, region, location have own policies and rules for non-profit organization. Difference sector have performed individual tasks to legalize accountabilities. (Jordan, L. & Van Tuijl, P. (Eds.), 2006).

3.2 Youth development programs

- Developing youth community is a crucial for society and regional development.
- Youth development programs can be leading to higher society. On the other hand, those can lead to opposite direction.
- Studying and analyzing programs outcome are central indicator for the future community outcome.

3.3 Basic Facts of the program

- Even VTPs have been training certain number of candidates in very year, certain number of youths are left out in every year.
- The interest and implementation on the VTPs of non-profit organization Vs youth community Vs society need are similar/ difference.

3.4 Measurement of Social impact of VTP organizations and VTP alumni

Market research analysis has been conducted in two sections, namely,

- A questionnaire survey administered on the employees of the organizations, and
- Participants of the VTP (Voluntary Training Program) Questionnaire

The analysis of the collection of the data from these two sections will formulate the data analysis and results of the social impact of the voluntary programs in the communities of the Myanmar. This methodology will imply the factors depending on the social benefits of the local participants as mentioned in one of the statements of Literature Review “socially-oriented ... programmed provide evidence on economic impact in the south Asian.” (Kabeer, N. (2005)). It is evident that the author wants to show the association in between the social, economic and environmental aspects of those two states in Myanmar.

Since Myanmar is a developing country it is required to be concern about the political and economic which impacts the social aspect of the country. Henceforth, the author also mentioned in the statement “Myanmar, impoverishment is increasing, with ever-larger proportions of the population unable to meet their basic needs” (Lorch, J. (2008)); to show how the large proportions of the population has been affected by the economic and political concern of the country.

3.5 Methodology of Questionnaire Administration - Conceptual Framework for Impact Assessment

The author has designed the two questionnaires i.e. a questionnaire survey administered on the employees of the organizations, and participants of the VTP (Voluntary Training Program) Questionnaire has been created at Vrij Universtat Brussels, Belgium with the guidance of Professor. Dr. Stijn Van Puyvelde, to study the social impact of the voluntary training programs in the community of Myanmar. In the research study the author will also discuss on the various social innovation that can be a part influencing the social aspect of Myanmar. “Social innovation

can and must come from all sectors—the public sector, the private market, the third sector, and individuals/household—and that many innovations move between sectors as they evolve” (SIE 2012, p. 19).

Figure 3-1 Social Innovation Business (SIE) modelling

3.6 Sample Size and Sample Selection

To start off with, 311 alumni participant’s questionnaires were issued by Google Survey and Analytics within the alumni society to understand and analysis the social impact and factors related with the VTP in the organizations. But only 131 participants came up with the response on the questions which is further discussed in the data analysis and results section.

Due to the pandemic situation of the coronavirus, the most of the organizations were reluctant to move forward with the questionnaires since the organizations were either closed or restricted to their own norms. On the positive note, there are 10 organizations mainly from Myanmar: Yangon, Mon State, Kayin State and Thailand: Mae Sot, which revert to the questionnaire survey which will help the author to analyze the social impact of the voluntary training programs created by the organizations.

3.6.1 Section 1: A questionnaire survey administered on the employee of the organizations,

- Cross validation of the questionnaire survey administered on the employees of the organizations only for the case study in the data analysis via data collection each question has been discuss, and

3.6.2 Section 2: Participants of the VTP (voluntary Training Program) Questionnaire

- Analyze in comparison with the socio economic aspect of Myanmar, Participants of the VTP (Voluntary Training Program) and innovated social business model for the development of the local community and improve social welfare.

It was difficult to go for another completion of questionnaire distribution to increase the number of Alumni participant's respondents and the number of the organizations due to the limitations on the time to complete the research study and it was a strenuous pandemic situation which is unlikely to change for a year or two. The author being based in Belgium and the respondents and the organizations are based in Myanmar which made it harder to collect the data.

3.7 Conclusion:

After the results and the data collection from the alumni participants and the organizations, the author understood the significance of the research study on the social impact of the voluntary training programs of the organizations. It led to the recommendations in analyzing the impact and strand of a successful research study.

It additionally helped in introductory presumptions with respect to research methodology would hence be to focus on the research study. **Appendix - 1 and 2 for the questionnaires, see the below section of data analysis and results section**

4 Data Analysis

4.1 Organizations with the Voluntary Programs:

The author was able to take information from 10 CBOs/NGOs organizations with the voluntary programs involving the Myanmar communities. They are mainly from South East Asia Myanmar and Thailand.

The organizations are ICJ (Parental Organization(PO) : Pa-O Youth Organization), Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program (PO : World Education, BMWEC, Child Dream), Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS), Zweekabin Myay, Mon National Education Committee, PointB Design and Training, Youth Learning Center, Bridge for All, English Immersion Program(PO : World Education(Thailand), Karen Refugee Committee Education Entity (KRCEE) – Thailand, Karen Education Department (Thailand) and Local Development Network.

There are 3 CBOs from Kayin State and Mon State from Thailand and 1 CBO from Mae Sot Thailand respectively and one non-governmental/non-profit organizations in each of the location including Yangon respectively as shown in the Table: 4-1

Type of organization	Location	Number of organizations
CBO/CSO	Kayin State	3
CBO/CSO	Mae Sot, Thailand	1
CBO/CSO	Mon State	3
NGO	Mae Sot, Thailand	1
NGO	Mon State	1
NGO	Yangon	1

Table 4-1 CBOs and NGOs location s and numbers

Figure 4-1 Type of Organization and locations

Operation of the organizations:

Q 9 :Years of operations : The years of operations of all the 10 organizations namely; ICJ (Parental Organization(PO) : Pa-O Youth Organization), Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program (PO : World Education, BMWEC, Child Dream), Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS), Zwekabin Myay, Mon National Education Committee, PointB Design and Training, Youth Learning Center, Bridge for All, English Immersion Program(PO : World Education(Thailand),

Karen Refugee Committee Education Entity (KRCEE) – Thailand, Karen Education Department (Thailand) and Local Development Network are 6 years, 14 Years, 80 years, 8 Years, 19 years, 7 Year, 7 Years, 5 Years, 17 Years, 5 Years respectively.

Question 7: What sector(s) do your organization operate in / do you represent?

When the author ask about the sectors the organizations operate or represent, most of the organizations is into the sector of education with 5 CBOs/NGOs. With 3 organizations in the vocational training, community development and youth empowerment sector. organizations are into Legal and human rights and livelihood activities. Only one organization are into the sector of capacity building, emergency assistance, advocacy and coordinating, networking sector as shown in the Organizational Working Sectors Fig: 4-2 and Table 4-2:

Education	5
Vocational Training,	3
Community Development	3
Youth Empowerment	3
Legal and human rights	2
Livelihood activities	2
Capacity building	1
Emergency assistance	1
Advocacy	1
coordinating/networking	1

Table 4-2 Organization Working Sectors

Figure 4-2 Organization Working Sectors

Q: 8 Could you please describe your organization aims, objectives, missions and vision?

In accordance to the Table: 4-3, the main aim, objectives, mission and vision of the organization are youth vocational, youth empowerment, education and livelihood with 4, 3, 4 and 1 respectively.

Youth vocational	4
Youth Empowerment	3
Education	4
Livelihood	1

Table 4-3 Organization Aims and Objective

Q 12: Name of the project/vocational program

The main vocational programs introduced by the organizations are Wide Horizons Program, Zweekabin Myay Hpa-an Education Project, Bop Htao Education Empowerment Program, Design Thinking for Community Engagement, Youth Learning Center, B4A - Bridge for All, English Immersion Program, Youth Empowerment training. These programs eventually have a he impacts on the social attributes towards improving the local community in Myanmar. According to ((OECD), 2008), to deal with a country's poverty and improve the socio-economical aspect these programs are definitely required from the likes of United States to the under developing countries like Myanmar, Turkey and Mexico.

When the author surveyed on the Q: 14 Could you please describe the motivation of the project/vocational program implementation? The organizations mainly referred to the social voluntary programs and one of them detailed the information as “Well reconstruction to get clear water for migrant community.” In most of the organizations, the participants/students tend to do the analytical assessment and in one of the organization the students were involved in some well define project such as Reproductive health right to the Mon Youth, Waste Management Campaign to the government primary school in Choung Zon and Sports project to the Mattama areas. In conclusion, from all three projects more than 2000 local people gain benefit from the student community projects via organizations. In few of the organizations which are focus on the education section such as Burmese community empowerment. One of the programs i.e. Zweekabin Myay focused on the gap in the higher education sector to empower participants by providing them the skills to maximize their potential. Empowering young adults from Burma with the skills and disposition, supporting and providing youth need in community needed to develop civil society through education is one of the priority for the organization who are focused on the community and education development.

The organization got committed staff who do not complain about financial issues, staff turnover rate is very low, and the villagers or community people are involving and helping the school to

develop and build the community based projects. There are programs focused on developing abilities and skills of the participants to help benefit their local communities.

"Q 19. Could you please describe three main criteria of student intake and why? "

When it comes to the main criteria for the student intake by the organizations are educational qualifications, age, training programs. The other reasons are commitment of student to work for community and organization, to become social activist and politician, educational qualification especially in English, computer and community Development subjects. In one of the organization "English proficiency, being a member of a CBO, aged 20 years and above. The reason being that the program aims to inspire individuals to become leaders in their communities, thus the age requirement, and training those who are already in the community development work will help steer the organization's vision in the right direction. The courses in the program were conducted in English and facilitated by foreign teachers, hence the language requirement." Hence it shows minimum level of age and training program has shown importance in the intake of the students pursuing the voluntary programs in the various organizations.

One of the organization member stated, "We run an intensive residential education and training program targeted at school leavers and university graduates from across the state because the program, taught through English, encompass a diverse curriculum." And another one stated "Young adults who have completed Mon National Education Committee (MNEC) high schools and/or Burmese government high schools. We have, however, also accepted MNEC teachers, staff from other Mon State based civil society organizations, distance university students and university graduates due to continuous requests." The social impact and various factor for the community development in Myanmar largely depends on the voluntary programs which further bring balance to the social, economic and environment of Myanmar.

The minimum requirement for the other organizations are design thinking – collaboration, empathy and beginner level of course with the English placement test with the enthusiasm to commit and learn and work in their community.

Q 20: As shown the Fig: 4-3 Organization versus the rating of the VTP’s funding. It is projected from the survey from the organizations questionnaire that the funding for the programs via international or national/government funding stated to be quite good in comparisons the fair, poor and very good. Most of the organizations stated good rating, and followed by fair, poor and one organization stated as very good as shown in the fig: below:

Figure 4-3 Organization Vs VTPs Funding

When the author stated on the organization questionnaire about the main important problems in the local community, there are health, poverty, unemployment, low rate of career opportunities, drugs which are closely related with the society. The organizations focuses on the vital problems in the Myanmar communities and the VTP mostly targets to counterpart the problems faced by the Myanmar people in their community as shown in the Table 4-4 below:

1. Name of the organization	2. What are the most important problems in that community?
ICJ	Health, Poverty, and Unemployment (high number of population)
Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program	Health, Education (Low range of literate population) Job, and Drug.
Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS)	Poverty, Education (Low range of literate population), Job & drugs, Low rate of career opportunities.
Zwekabin Myay	Education (Low range of literate population), Job, Drugs, Unemployment (high number of population), Low rate of career opportunities.
Mon National Education Committee	Poverty, Education (Low range of literate population), Job, drug, Unemployment (high number of population), Low rate of career opportunities.
PointB Design and Training	Poverty, Low rate of career opportunities, Drug.

Youth Learning Center	Poverty, Education (Low range of literate population), Job, drug, Unemployment (high number of population), Low rate of career opportunities, Drug.
Bridge for All	Education (Low range of literate population), Job, drug, Low rate of career opportunities.
English Immersion Program	Poverty, Education (Low range of literate population), Job, drug, Low rate of career opportunities.
Local Development Network	Health, Poverty, Education (Low range of literate population), Job, drug, Unemployment (high number of population)

Table 4-4 Organizations assessment of community problems

4.2 Project Input Functions for the VT-programs

The author questioned on the starting year of the VTP in their organizations and the number of implementations of the vocational training programs. As shown in the Table 4-5; most of the programs started in the 20th century and during the first decade of the century such as Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) started contributing to the community since 2000 along with Mon National Education committee. Organizations like ICJ, Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program, and English Immersion Program start their VTPs in the year of 2007, 2006 and 2013 respectively as in the Table 4-5 below:

There has been number of vocational training programs that has been implemented in Myanmar for the social welfare of the community. The most number of VTPs has been develop by Wide Horizons Organizational Development with 200 programs followed by Local Development Network with 43 programs. Youth Learning Centre with 20 programs followed by English Immersion Program with 16 programs under their belt. ICJ organizations with 1, Zweekabin Myay with 7, Mon National Education Committee with 9, PointB design and training and Bridge for all with 1 and 5 respectively as shown in the Table 4-5 below:

1. Name of the organization	When did the project/vocational program start?	How many project/vocational program has been implemented?
ICJ	2007	1
Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program	2006	200
Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS)	Since 2000	

Zwekabin Myay	2012	7
Mon National Education Committee	2000	9
PointB Design and Training	2014	1
Youth Learning Center	July 2014	20
Bridge for All	2015	5
English Immersion Program	2003	16
Local Development Network	2015	43

Table 4-5 Organization history

Furthermore, the author also stated about the duration of the Vocational Training Programs given by the organizations. Five organizations has developed programs with a duration of 1 year or more. Three organizations has developed programs with a span of three to six months as shown in the Fig 4-4 below. Two of the organizations create VTP having duration within the span of 6 months to 1 year. From this analysis, the author relates to the programs with the durations to see the comparisons of the participants learning capabilities during the period and henceforth, figure out if the participants are willing to return to the community for the social welfare after graduation. Most of the organizations have one or more year programs for the participants to develop the skills to reach their potential and help in designing the new community with social innovation business models after completion of the program. **(SIE, 2003).**

Figure 4-4 Duration of the programs

As shown the Fig 4-5; Local Development Network with a selection of 50 participants for their Vocational Training Programs, while Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program with 24, Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) with 20, Zweekabin Myay and Mon National Education Committee with 20 and 24 participants respectively. The organization, ICJ with 15 participants for its VTPs.

PointB Design and Training and Youth Learning Center with 25 and 20 participants respectively. Bridge for All and English Immersion Program each with an involvement of 20 participants and Karen Education Department with 25 as shown below:

Figure 4-5 Selected participants in each program

Q 26: Total number of graduate participants?

As shown the Fig 4-6; ICJ with total number of 15 graduate students whereas Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program with 300 total number of graduate students. Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) with 18, Zwekabin Myay with 140 graduate participants and Mon National Education Committee with 216 participants.

PointB Design and Training and Youth Learning Center with 80 and 400 participants. Bridge for All and English Immersion Program each with an involvement of 54 participants and Karen Education Department with 1984, Local Development Network with 2000 showing the highest number graduated participants of amongst all the organizations. It shows the primary focus on the social impact of VTP are education and community development as shown below in Fig: 4-6

Figure 4-6 Total number of graduate participants

When the author questioned on “Q 28 What are the main courses teach in vocational program?”

The most significant common courses in the vocation programs of the organizations are computer skills, English and Community service and social awareness. Few of the organizations focusses on the management, research, leadership and analytical skills. The other crucial learning paths are design and system thinking. Social studies, networking, Youth Empowerment and Livelihood

program are the main ones for the organizations to develop programs to enhance the skills of the participants/students while enrolled in the VTPs.

When it comes to the graduated participants from the VTPs; ICJ has total of number of 15 participants returning back to their community after completion of their degree, Wide Horizons Organizational Development Program got a total of 240 graduated participants. Unfortunately, Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) statistics shows 0 number of the participants actually go back for the social welfare of the community.

The following organizations have the same number of graduate participants who revert to the social welfare of the community such as Zwekabin Myay with a total of 110, on National Education Committee with a total participants of 216, PointB Design and Training with 50 in total, Youth Learning Center with a total number of 400 students, Bridge for All with 29. The organizations: With a 100% of participants/students goes back to the social welfare of the their community when it comes to the big organization such as English Immersion Program with 1984, Local Development Network with 2000 as shown in the Figure 4-7 below

Figure 4-7 Participants return to Community

4.3 Voluntary Training Programs – Participants Alumni Questionnaire

The author was able to collect 132 alumni participants' questionnaires in order to focus on the social impact of the VTPs in Myanmar. Out of 132 participants, nearly 64 were females and 68 male participants as shown in the Fig 4-8: The average of the participants were in the range of 26-35 compared with the range of young participants 15-25 and the lowest of the older participants with the range of 36-50 as shown in the Fig 4-8

Figure 4-9 Gender

Figure 4-8 Age

The current status of the participants are mostly employed with more than 100 participants yet the question lies if they all went back for the social welfare community development. The second highest participants were still students' part of the VTPs with nearly 25 in total. When it comes to trainee and unemployed it is less than 15 participants which states that the alumni with the VTPs have mostly been employed and working. Its shows how VTPs programs helps in developing the potential skills of the participants with the program as shown in the Fig: 4-8

Figure 4-10 Participants current status

The author while questioning about the location of the VTPs its Kayin State with 45 participants where Mon state with 22 participants and Shan State with 15 participants. The rest of the participants got deployed in the smaller states in the south eastern countries such as Kuala Lumpur, Yangon, Shan State, Mandalay, Chinag Mai, Montreal, Kentucky, Kachin State, Phop Phra, Tanintharyi and Chin State as shown in the Fig 4-11

Figure 4-11 Location of Participants

According to the author, there were three graduate programs that helped the VTPs students to get involved with the community and they are EIP- English Immersion Program, WH – Wide Horizons Program and B4A – Bridge for All. Wide Horizon Program stays at the highest with 50 participants while EIP – English Immersion Program with 45 and B4 A – Bridge for all with 25 participants. These are the main voluntary training programs that has been valued for the participants to develop and create and build their own local community.

Figure 4-12 Name of the graduate program

The maximum of the participants are involved in professions after VTPs like teachers, trainers, coordinators, project managers.

Figure 4-13 Current position of participant

The question was asked for how many months did the participants attend the VTPs of the organizations. The maximum participants with a number for 120 were involved with VTPs by the organizations for more than 1 year programs. The rest within 3 to 6 months of programs around 12 participants as shown in the Fig 4-14

Figure 4-14 Period of the program attend by participant

While the author holds the question on graduating from the programs. 55 alumni participants got graduated from the VTP programs in the range of 2016 to 2020 which shows the improvement and progress of the social aspect of the country. In order to reach that, it will also influence the economy and environmental sector of Myanmar. In the range of 2011 to 2015 years, nearly 50 participants got graduated; with a conclusion of an advancement of the last decade in the country's 3 BL as shown in the in the Fig 4-15: The least number of participants got graduated in the first decade of 20th century.

Figure 4-15 Period of graduated

When it comes to rating the challenges faced by the participants during the program, its fairly noticeable from the Fig 4-16 that most of the participants i.e. 80 participants found it difficult. Less than 50 participants found it usual, and 10 participants found it easy and with the least number of participants found it very difficult.

Figure 4-16 Level of Challenges to attend program

Upon rating the overall quality of the Vocational Training Programs, 75 of the participants were overall satisfied with the program with little bit less than 60 participants were very satisfied. Neutral with 5 participants, not satisfied none. It shows the eagerness of the participants to improve the quality of social aspect of the community and reflects on the socio-economical aspect of the society in Myanmar.

Figure 4-17 Overall quality of the program

While the author trying to understand the learning experience for their own potential growth, 75 participants were satisfied while 50 participants with a very satisfied result and neutral only with 5 participants.

Figure 4-18 Overall learning experience

The author asked the Q"14. Please list three important skills that you learned from this program?"

The analysis of the this question figures out the participants were involved with English, project management teaching, language, management, social and communication, organizational development, advanced computer skill, cross-culture understanding.

The other skills what the participants develop are public speaking skill, program and project management and English speaking and writing skill, leadership, and problem solving, management, interpersonal skill, communication skill, and critical thinking skill, translation.

Proposal writing , Community Development, negotiations skills, proposals and report writing skill, , reading, video editing., classroom management, lesson planning and computer skills are the ones the participants greatly develop with the VTPs organized by the organizations as shown in the Fig 1-19

Figure 4-19 Important Subjects

The author also surveyed on the part of the recommendations the VTPs to their close ones and more than 100 participants came up with a positive reply while 25 participants were into recommended. The rest of participants seems to be pretty agile and the number of participants is very low with, “not recommended: as 10 participants, 15 participants were neutral and no recommendation with 5 participants as shown in the Fig 4-20:

Figure 4-20 Recommend to others

When it comes to the outlook from the participants with the overview of the VTPs, 82 participants stated the requirement of these voluntary programs for the community. Maybe more than one in the community. 35 participants stated the requirement of the programs for the community and a single program is good for each community with 9 participants as shown in the Table 4-6:

17. What is your recommendation for the existence of the program for the community? [Recommend that]	Count of 17. What is your recommendation for the existence of the program for the community? [Recommend that]
1 is enough	9
Need more in other region	35

Needs few more in the community	82
---------------------------------	----

Table 4-6 Recommendation for existence

Coming on the most important question, the author surveyed on the job placements after graduating from the VTPs from the organizations. Nearly 75 participants stated to be easy while intermediate were of 35 participants. With 5 participants and 20 participants stated difficult and usual respectively as shown in the Fig 4-21

Figure 4-21 Get job rate after graduation

Comparing the job and educational opportunities after the VTPs, nearly 115 participants stated it is easy to find a job or further studies. It relates to the beneficial and the progressive nature of these VTPs when it comes to understanding the community. As shown in the Fig 4-22: 15 participants stated it is very easy to get hands on to a job or education while 10 participants and 5 participants shows that neutral and difficult respectively.

Figure 4-22 Compare job or education before and after the program

On the contradictory part; the author went on with the kind of organizations the participants worked for after their graduation. As shown in the Fig 4-23: most of the participants worked for CBOs/CSOs with 92 participants. Nearly 28 participants work for the NGOs and the rest for education, own business holders, refugee, student, private company.

Figure 4-23 Type of organization worked after graduated

The author surveyed on the nature of the participants work after completion of the VTPs. More than 30 participants work as a field officer and teacher while 14 participants work as a trainer. Less than 10 participants work in the field of coordinator, operation, accountant, manager, nurse staff, and journalist as shown in Fig 4-24 below

Figure 4-24 Nature of work after graduated

55 participants works in Kayin State of Myanmar and rest of the participants work in the different states of Myanmar such as Yangon, Shan state, Kachin state, Mandalay, Umpham, Phop Phra, chin state and very few of the participants work in the Thailand and Bangkok with a number of 5 and 2 respectively as shown in the Fig 4-25 below

Figure 4-25 Location of the organization that work after graduated

55 participants work more than 5 years in the particular organization while 38 of the participants work in the range of 0 to 2 years and 32 participants worked in between 2-5 years. Only 2 participants work for 3 years as shown in the Fig. 4-26

Figure 4-26 Period of worked in the organization

While mentioning about the skills which were part of the voluntary training programs, 75 of the participants stated that it was useful while 55 of the participants stated as very useful with the current job designations. It reflects on the social impact of the voluntary programs in Myanmar and 2 participants stated as neutral and useless respectively as shown in the Fig 4-27:

Figure 4-27 Skills that learned form program

In the Table 4-7 below, the author tries to find out the increment of their income after the completion of the VTPs. 73 participants have an increase of from 0 – 10% while 27 of the participants have the percentage increase of 10 to 15. 15% or more with 11 participants and neutral by 19 participants. It shows the importance of the VTPs programs that increases the income after graduating from these programs. It has a pure impact on the socio-economic aspect of Myanmar.

25. Did your income increase or decrease after graduating from the program?	Count of 25. Did your income increase or decrease after graduating from the program?
Increase (0 -10%)	73
Increase (10% -15%)	27
Increase (15 % or more)	11
Same	19

Table 4-7 Income increase or decrease

Before joining the VTPs, the author creates a question on the formal education of the participants. As shown in the Table 4-8, 81 of the participants has associate certification or a college diploma. Graduate degree holder and pursuing PhD are left with 13 participants while 37 of the participants has high school certification.

26. What was your formal education before joining the program?	What was your formal education before joining the program?
Associate certification/college diploma	81
Graduate degree or PhD	13
High School	37

Table 4-8 formal education before program

As an associate question, the author states the present education level after completion of the VTPs in Myanmar as shown in the Fig 4-28

Figure 4-28 Current formal education

The current formal education; 79 of the participants has a graduate degree or PhD which shows the improvement in the academic sector. 43 of the participants holds associate certification or a college diploma and 9 participants hold a high school certification as shown in the Table 4-9 below. It is noticeable with improvement in the academics and VTPs skills and activities, the participants do get a perfect combination to enhance the career growth.

27. What is your current formal education level?	Count of 27. What is your current formal education level?
Associate certification/college diploma	43
Graduate degree or PhD	79
High School	9

Table 4-9 Current formal education level

5 Results

5.1 Hypothesis

“Making a difference to livelihoods and capacities among poor people depends on NGO successes in fostering autonomous grassroots institutions and linking them with markets and political structures at higher levels.” (Edwards, M. (1999). The author would like to state about the consequences of the socio-economic aspect of Myanmar with the political situation by surveying the 10 organizations and 131 alumni participants through data collection. From the data analysis it can be seen that Educational programs are most effective ones. Comparing the analysis of the data from the employee of the organization, alumni participant and the VTP has a huge impact on local community development.

Organizations such as ICJ, Wide Horizon Organizational Development program, Jesuit Refugee Service and Bridge for all played a vital role in displaying the Vocational Training Program involving the youth to improve the community sector. All these organization got an increase number of the graduates in the recent years which shows in the improvement of an individual career growth along with their potential skills. It shows a growing number of graduate participants/alumni tend to go back to their own community and enhance the socio-economic aspect of Myanmar.

When it comes to alumni participants, majority who filled the questionnaire were male while female is still lagging behind in the area of the VTP. Maximum of the participants are working while a small percentage are unemployed. Since the author has more communities and networking in the communities like Kayin and Mon state in Myanmar, more organizations and participants have been involved in the data collection and data analysis.

After interviewing the participants, there has been significant improvement in the livelihood, education system and community development in the local community of Mon state and Kayin State.

After the analysis the data collection both organizations and alumni participants stated about the huge impact on the socio-economic aspect of the states via vocational training programs. The survey also showed 0-10% increase in the income due to Vocational Training Programs or VET involving 89 participants out of 131 participants in total.

The beneficitation of SIE's social innovation business models with its state of art, new research study and its dimensions (communications, products and its process) also has been generated due to involvement of the participants in the Vocational Training Programs especially after completion of the programs. Both organizations and alumni participants plays a vital role in uplifting and bring the society together linking with the social innovation business models.

Education sector is the most important occupation stated by the alumni participants with the VTP such as Volunteering trainee, youth empowerment, community development programs, legal and human right and life improvement.

The demerits of the socio-economic aspect of Myanmar are health poverty, drugs, and unemployment and these factors are the basic concern having a negative impact on the society, VTPs and influences the socio-economy of Myanmar.

Vocational Training Program funding are good in accordance to the alumni participant questionnaire survey outcome. According to the alumni participants the most effective and important skills are learning English, computer basic skills and community development.

More the duration of the program, more satisfactory and potential skills outcome has been shown by the alumni participants. Alumni participants highly recommended to improve the community development which concerns the local people because find a job or employability and even for further education after the VTP. According to the data, 92 participants returned to the CBOs/CSOs linked with community development and teaching skills.

Henceforth, the organizations play an important role through these Vocational Training Programs towards the improvement of the community development and enhance the potential skills of alumni participants. The youth development program plays a crucial role for an alumni participant's career growth. On the political stand of Myanmar, the situation still lacks and influences the source of the international funding towards the VTPs and as a results affects the community development.

6 Discussions

This research study enables to understand the view of the VTPs of the organizations and alumni participants and the community needs as stated “Across Myanmar, impoverishment is increasing, with ever-larger proportions of the population unable to meet their basic needs.” (Lorch, J. (2008). To give a fair idea when dealing with the 131 participants survey and 10 organizations mainly in Myanmar and couple of them in Thailand; it is prompt that vocational training programs has given a boost to the community needs, participants and the organizations.

6.1 Alumni Participants Perspective on VTPs

From the alumni participant questionnaire shows the improvement of the social impact of the voluntary training programs and advancement of the individual quality life with the increase in the household income and social welfare. A high number of participants also stated that it is easier for the participants to find a job or a career growth after completion of the VTPs in Myanmar.

A large number of the participants were satisfied with the learning experience and the potential skills that the participants have develop and used in their current work or academia which also has a good social impact on the societies/states of Myanmar with the development and increase of the VTPs by the organizations.

6.2 Non-profit organizations Perspective on Community

With the insight of the organization interview questionnaire knowing about the number of participants involved in the VTPs and helps out with the community development such as in the fields of English, management skills, critical thinking during their voluntary training program.

With the number of participants graduating from the program and number of the participants who actually gets involved with the social welfare and community development seems to have a similar total number except of couple of organizations. This section will help in understanding the participants/alumni questionnaire in the following section.

6.3 Employment Opportunities

“Results are frequently not convincing for various reasons. Above all the decision-making foundations are scarcely of any use for the individual and for companies and State authorities.” (Van Lith, U. ,1998). Sometimes the outcomes of a research study might not be convincing, but this research study has got a significant amount of data collection and analysis to deal with appropriate results. As discussed earlier, the socio-economic impact of the vocational training programs also reflects on the employment opportunities while asking the participants, a large percentage of the VTPs holders stated that the employment opportunities has increased after completion of the program which has been discuss below.

The decision making on the organizing a vocational training programs requires a lot of dedication and collaboration from the organizations – CBOs/NGOs with the state government authorities to improve the lives of the youth and bring the potential skills into market. It has been seen that fair amount of participants do go back to their community in order to improve the status of the local people. The author wants to state about the provinces like Mon and Kayin State where there more vocational training programs compared to other states like Yangon. The progress and growth definitely can be seen in those former states with the high employability rate than the rest of the country.

These participants also play an important in developing social innovation business models after completion of the program and bringing in new models to uplift the economic and social aspect of the community.

6.4 Social Innovation Business Models:

The Social Innovation Europe³ (SIE) notes that “social innovation can and must come from all sectors—the public sector, the private market, the third sector, and individuals/household—and that many innovations move between sectors as they evolve.” (SIE 2012, p. 19).

Figure 6-1 Social Innovation Business (SIE) modelling

As discussed in the literature review, a gist of the social innovative models can play a crucial role to help to community grow by having a vigilant watch on the needs of the community. The states of Myanmar are poor and the low income market definitely makes the citizen struggle with their flow of income. As seen from the data collection and analysis, the participants involved in the VTPs, their income rate has increased from 0-10% voted by 80 participants.

Around 30 participants stated 15% increment in their income after completion of the vocational training programs. These participants can also play a vital role in developing social innovative models in the community with their knowledge, ideas and thought process. The dimensions of the social innovation models can become a shared valued; the importance of the networking and communications; creation of a product and the process to improve the lives of their neighbors and surrounding regions.

The organizations can too play its role by creating the innovative business models as mentioned by the author in the literature review. “Innovative business models can generate different types of enterprises as new age enterprises, social enterprises, community-based enterprises, hybrid organizations and inclusive businesses.” (Westall 2007; CII-ITC CESD 2010). These social innovative business model can lead way for the improvement of the community by both organizations – VTPS and the alumni participants.

6.5 Collaborations

Collaborations in between the organizations with international NGOs or with the governmental bodies, mix collaboration with the alumni participants to create a social innovative model can also play a big part in the development of the socio-economic aspect of the communities in Myanmar. These collaborations can have a growth in a unique by looking at the questionnaires filled by the organizations and alumni participants. Further it can be stated that role of the organizations and alumni participants or their combinations can be a largely beneficial to the communities in Myanmar.

7 Conclusion

To conclude with, the author would like to state on the social impact of the vocational training programs by the organizations. The author would like to conclude in four different aspects namely; Risk Evaluations of the social impact of the VTPs, Strengths of the vocational training programs for future research in the social-economic aspect of Myanmar, limitations of the research study and scope of the research study.

7.1 Risk Evaluations:

The author would like to discuss about the risk evaluation of the social impact of the voluntary programs and in this research study the author surveyed both from the organizations and alumni participants to get a broader idea about the social aspects happening in the study.

As we discussed in the literature review about the author Gibbon and Dey (2011) statement of:

While some question whether frameworks based on the private sector experience are entirely suitable, others argue that unless organizations use frameworks and language that are recognized by the wider system of decision-making in our mixed economy of welfare, the value and achievements of social purpose organizations will not be acknowledged. **(Gibbon & Dey, 2011, p. 68).**

the author would like to state about the frameworks or the business models used by the organizations to develop the vocational training programs for the youth. But there are a lot of risk while developing the programs due to the political situation in Myanmar is always a prime concern.

Corruption and bribery also play its role while funds get distribute to the organizations. The question is “where do the money go?” It can be either gone to the governmental bodies/political parties or to the organizations. The real problem is always faced by the communities since Myanmar communities depends on the vocational programs to enhance their income.

“Considerable progress has been made in regression and factor analyses and in distinguishing between parameters such as natural talent, origin and social environment, practical work experience, educational results, productivity, educational return and career opportunities.” (Van Lith, U., 1998) There are always a risk when it comes to religious ethics of Myanmar. In the recent years, there has been social unrest and clash in between the Buddhist and Muslim communities in the country. These clash hampers the VTPs and outreach the communities since the citizens are more concern about their origins and social environment. It also reflects on the educational outcomes, the skills and productivity and work opportunities.

Moreover, the socio-economic impact the growth of the countries especially organizations, governmental bodies and communities are associated with the socio-economical disputes in the country.

7.2 Strengths:

The author would like state the tremendous strengths of the vocational training programs in the communities of Myanmar as stated in the literature review journal: “A conspicuous trend in the development of the contemporary world is the growing role of nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) in politics, the economy, and sociocultural progress.” (Diachenko, S., 2007). With the number of the growing non-profit organizations and developing and organizing the VTPs there can be growth in the social, economic and environment growth in the country.

It reflects on the progressive nature of the programs that underline the benefits the community gets from these programs. In the field of politics, economy and sociocultural growth can be seen while developing VTPs in the country by the various organizations.

7.3 Limitations of the study:

The research study on social impact of the vocational training programs there can be seen a lot of limitations. Vocational training programs may not be feasible for the organizations. The research study topic itself is a broad subject. Sample size considerations for the organizations and the participants can be too big or small. The data collection was quite hard since the author lives in Belgium and the whole research study is for Myanmar.

There were 311 alumni participants were given out and just got 131 replies from the participants. The target for the organizations was 30 but ended with 10 organizations with proper interview questions. The possible consideration of the less data collection than expected was mainly due to the closure of the organizations due to global COVID-19 situation and conflict of local and national military army in Karen and Mon State. The technological difficulty such as internet connections plays an important role since Myanmar is an underdeveloped country and to outreach the local societies becomes little bit problematic. The language barrier also plays a role when it comes to data collection.

People are familiar with their own national language or dialects and a very few of them can understand English since this research has been spread out in English. But all the 10 organizations (Appendix 1) and 132 participants (Appendix 2) has filled the questionnaires to their best knowledge and was enough to conclude the research study.

7.4 Future scope of the research study:

The future scope of the research study is very prospective and can be seen greatly affect the minds of the local citizens in Myanmar. It will help the citizens of the country to understand the social impact of the VTPs in the country and will help them develop knowledge of the VTPS. From the organizations point of view, there can more international European universities or Non-profit organization help, fund and promote the VTPs in Myanmar.

At last but not the least, this research study can significantly lead to a post-doctoral research topic and further explored and unify the social impact of the vocational training programs in Myanmar. With the insight of the future scope of the research study, the author would like to comment on the benefits for the organizations, governmental and the local communities through the vocational training programs (**Diachenko, S., 2007**). The social innovations through new business models will play an important role in the future scope of this research study.

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***Please note: Google scholar articles, journals, web links (Good impact factor) and books are related with this research study references.**

Annex 1: Nonprofit organization Survey

Nonprofit organization Survey

Dear Sir/Madam:

My name is Salai Tun Lin Aung and thank in advance for your participating in this questionnaire. The purpose of conducting this survey is an essential part of my master thesis “Social impact of nonprofit programs: case study focused on Myanmar” for MSc in Management at the VUB, Brussels, Belgium.

It will take only 5~10 minutes to finish the survey.

Your data are confidential. This research is an academic purpose only, nothing concerns with any government, nor any organization, group in any form. All the names of the person and organization will not be seen or display at any from. Moreover, your answer will not be shared with anyone and will be kept absolutely confidential and will be compiled with other answers. There will be only statistical summarize present and the results will be used for academic purpose only.

The purpose of the study. This study will assess social impact of empowering youth by nonprofit organizations. Therefore, conducting this “alumni survey” and “organization survey” will provide data to summarize. Understanding of those social impact can be indicate future recommendation.

Your response and time are greatly appreciated. If you have any questions or concerns please do not hesitate to email salai.tun.lin.aung@vub.ac.be and salaihtunlin@gmail.com.

Organization information

1. Name of the organization

2. Type of organization

Check all that apply.

NGO

CBO/CSO

Other: _____

3. Location

Please write in English

4. Website URL / Facebook URL

5. Contact person

Please write in English.

6. Contact e-mail

Please write in English

7. What sector(s) do your organization operate in / do you represent?

Example: Education (administration of schools, specialized education, training or career development),

8. Could you please describe your organization aims, objectives, missions and vision?

Please write in English

9. How long your organization have been operating?

Please write in English.

10. Could you please describe the number of your parental organizations and their names?

Please write in English

11. What are the government / local authority's policies for type of your organization?

Please write in English

Vocational project information

12. Name of the project/vocational program

Please describe in English.

Check all that apply.

- EIP - English Immersion Program
- WH - Wide Horizons Program
- B4A - Bridge for All

Other: _____

13. Location of the project/vocational program

Please describe in English.

14. Could you please describe the motivation of the project/vocational program implementation?

Please describe in English.

15. Could you please describe the project/vocational program aims, objectives missions and vision?

Please describe in English.

16. What are the most important problems in that community?

Please describe in English.

Check all that apply.

Health

Poverty

Education (Low rate of literate population) , Job, drug,

Unemployment (high number of population)

Low rate of career opportunities

Drug

Other: _____

17. When did the project/vocational program start?

Please describe in English.

18. How many project/vocational program has been implemented?

Please describe in English.

19. Could you please describe three main criteria of student intake and why?

Please describe in English.

20. How would you rate the project/vocational program funding?

Mark only one oval per row.

Funding

- Excellent
- Very good
- Good
- Fair
- Poor

21. How would you rate the donor's influence on the project/vocational program implementation?

Mark only one oval per row.

Donors influence

- Not at all
- Fair
- Neutral
- Strong
- Very strong

22. Could you please describe three main challenges you were facing during the project?
What are the 3 main challenges in English.

23. Are there other programs those are similar to yours program in the community?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Vocational program information

24. Average number of candidates apply to the vocational program during new intake?
Please write in English.

25. Number of selected participants in each vocational program?
Please write in English.

26. Total number of graduate participants?

Please write in English.

27. How many months per year do the vocational program operating? (Training period)

Check all that apply.

- 3 months - 6 months
- 6 months - 1 year
- 1 year or more

28. What are the main courses teach in vocational program?

Please write in English.

29. How many graduated participants return to work for their community after completion of the program?

Please write in English.

Annex 2: Alumni Survey

Alumni Survey

Dear Alumni:

My name is Salai Tun Lin Aung and thank in advance for your participating in this questionnaire. The purpose of conducting this survey is an essential part of my master thesis “Social impact of nonprofit programs: case study focused on Myanmar” for MSc in Management at the VUB, Brussels, Belgium.

It will take only 3 ~ 5 minutes to finish the survey.

Your data are confidential. This research is an academic purpose only, nothing concerns with any government, nor any organization, group in any form. All the names of the person and organization will not be seen or display at any from. Moreover, our answer will not be shared with anyone and will be kept absolutely confidential and will be compiled with other answers. There will be only statistical summarize present and the results will be used for academic purpose only.

The purpose of the study. This study will assess social impact of empowering youth by nonprofit organizations. Therefore, conducting this “alumni survey” and “organization survey” will provide data to summarize. Understanding of those social impact can be indicate future recommendation.

Your response and time are greatly appreciated. If you have any questions or concerns please do not hesitate to email salai.tun.lin.aung@vub.ac.be or salaihtunlin@gmail.com

1. Name

2. Gender

Mark only one

- Male
- Female
- Other

3. Age

Mark only one.

- 15-25

- 26-35
- 36-50
- 51 or more

4. Current Status

Mark only one

- Work
- Student
- Unemployed
- Trainee

5. Current place of work / study

Please write the name of organization in English.

6. Location

Please write in English.

7. Current position/ program

Please write in English.

8. Name of the graduate program

Please write in English.

Mark only one

- EIP - English Immersion Program
- WH - Wide Horizons Program
- B4A - Bridge for All
- Other: _____

9. How many months did you attend the program?

Mark only one oval.

- 3 moths - 6 months
- 6 months - 1 year
- 1 year or more

10. When did you graduate from the program?
Please write in English.

11. How would you rate the level of challenge to attend program?
What was level of difficulty to attend the program?

Mark only one oval per row.

Entrance applying

- Very easy
- Easy
- Usual
- Difficult
- Very difficult

12. How would you rate the overall quality of the program course?

Mark only one oval per row.

Quality

- Very Satisfied
- Satisfied
- Natural
- Unsatisfied
- Very Unsatisfied

13. How would you rate your overall learning experience of the program?

Mark only one oval per row.

Learning experience

- Very Satisfied
- Satisfied
- Natural
- Unsatisfied
- Very Unsatisfied

14. Please list three important skills that you learned from this program?
Please write 3 important skills in English.

15. Please list three most important subjects you learned from this program course?
Please write 3 important subjects in English.

16. Will you recommend this program to others? If yes, please rate it below

Mark only one oval per row.

I Will

- Not recommend
- Natural
- Recommend
- Highly recommend
- No Answer

17. What is your recommendation for the existence of the program for the community?

Mark only one oval per row.

Recommend that

- Should not exist
- 1 is enough
- Needs few more in the community
- Need more in other region
- No answer

18. How easy was it to get a job after graduating?

Mark only one oval per row.

Got Job

- Immediately
- Easy
- Usual
- Difficult
- Very difficult

19. Compare job or education opportunities before and after the program.
It compares

Mark only one oval per row.

After the program

- Very easy
- Easy
- Same
- Difficult
- Very difficult

20. What type of organization did you work for after graduation?

Mark only one oval.

- Private Company
- NGO
- CBO/CSO
- Own Business
- Other: _____

21. Could you please describe the nature of your work after graduation?

Mark only one oval.

- Accountant
- Coordinator
- Director
- Field officer
- Journalist
- Manager
- Nurse
- Operation officer
- Researcher
- Reporter
- Teacher
- Trainer
- Other: _____

22. Location of the organization:

Please write in English. E.g. Hpa-An, Kayin State.

23. How long did you work for that organization?

Mark only one oval.

- 0 to 2 years
- 2 to 5 years
- 5 years or more

24. How would you rate the skills you had learned from the program applied at work?

Mark only one oval per row.

Skills are

- Very useful
- Useful
- Same
- Can't apply at my work
- Not practical
- Useless

25. Did your income increase or decrease after graduating from the program?

Mark only one oval per row.

Income were

- Decrease (0 to -10%)
- Same
- Increase (0 -10%)
- Increase (10% -15%)
- Increase (15 % or more)

26. What was your formal education before joining the program?

Please write in English.

Mark only one oval.

- High School
- Associate certification/college diploma
- Graduate degree or PhD
- Other: _____

27. What is your current formal education level?

Please write in English.

Mark only one oval.

- High School
- Associate certification/college diploma
- Graduate degree or PhD
- Other: _____